

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable D8.3

Deliverable: D8.3 EOSC integration plan (final)

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D8.3 EOSC integration plan (final)

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NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the ‘Prototyping New Innovative Services’ challenge set out in the ‘Roadmap for EOSC’ foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community’s research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

NEANIAS develops thematic services for EOSC communities on the field of Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. The project will integrate the thematic services into the EOSC ecosystem after they reach the maturity required by EOSC. This deliverable presents up-to-date information on EOSC integration approaches and procedures, as well as on relevant services discovered as part of the EOSC landscape monitoring activity.

This document updates the EOSC integration strategy and roadmap, initially described in Deliverable D8.1 [28], taking into account the current status and developments both at EOSC and NEANIAS levels. The document initially reviews the current status and developments in EOSC landscape, highlighting issues related to EOSC integration at all levels; service onboarding process, architecture, interfaces, federated services, service management, etc. Similarly, it briefly presents the NEANIAS services (both thematic and core ones) to be integrated to EOSC.

Having analysed the external and internal environment of the project (i.e. EOSC landscape and NEANIAS services' status, respectively), the deliverable focuses on the EOSC services which are targeted for integration with NEANIAS relevant services, and presents the updated plan for EOSC integration, which will serve as the guide for EOSC integration activities until the end of the project.

1. Introduction

The NEANIAS EU project aims to develop and integrate services to EOSC in the field of Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. The objective is to share these thematic services with scientific researchers of EOSC communities on these fields.

This deliverable is an update of Deliverable D8.1 “EOSC integration plan” [28], submitted in July 2020. At the time of writing this deliverable, the project has already onboarded five (5) thematic services to EOSC marketplace, while the plans for onboarding the remaining thematic services to EOSC are under finalisation. At the same time, the project is investigating the possibility of onboarding a number of core services to EOSC as well, thus exceeding the targets initially set for the availability of NEANIAS services on EOSC marketplace. The service onboarding process is facilitated by WP8, as regards procedural and management issues, and WP7, as regards the technical aspects of the integration process.

This deliverable has been written based on the current EOSC landscape, which is a continuously evolving environment, and provides up-to-date information as regards several fields related to EOSC integration, such as architecture, interfaces, access mechanism, federated services and so on.

The structure of this document is as follows: Section 2 starts with a short overview of EOSC in order to give an insight to the initiative and its landscape. In Section 3, the integration guidelines are summarised including the different integration approaches, the key components (e.g. EOSC portal and marketplace), federated services, data management and service management system. The NEANIAS services to be integrated to EOSC are introduced in Section 4. Section 5 overviews the available EOSC services which are targeted for integration with NEANIAS relevant services. Section 6 presents the EOSC integration plan (roadmap) and finally the conclusions are presented in Section 7.

2. Overview of European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a European Commission initiative aiming at a trusted, virtual, federated environment in Europe to store, share and re-use digital output from research (publications, data and software) across borders and scientific disciplines. The envisaged infrastructure is established by aggregating services, software, data and other types of scientific outputs from a diverse set of providers.

The EOSC initiative started in 2015, with the first version of the European Open Science Cloud officially launched in November 2018, with the EOSC Portal entry point (<https://eosc-portal.eu/>). The development of EOSC was initially governed by three bodies:

- The Executive Board, a body tasked to ensure implementation and accountability.
- The Governance Board of EOSC is an institutional group gathering representatives from the Member States and Associated Countries and from the Commission to ensure effective supervision of the EOSC implementation.
- The Stakeholder Forum is the community actively contributing and participating to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). It is composed by organisations, projects and initiatives fully committed to support the EOSC vision.

In July 2020, the **EOSC Association** was set up to provide a single voice for advocacy and represent the broader EOSC stakeholder community. It was established as a legal entity on 29th July 2020 with four (4) founding members: GÉANT, CESAER, CSIC and GARR and as of November 2020, 138 organizations participate as provisional members and about 50 as provisional observers¹. Besides GARR, members of the association from NEANIAS consortium are ATHENA, INAF, OpenAire.

The new governance model agreed with EU countries for the next EOSC implementation phase after 2020 will be tripartite including:

- The EU, represented by the Commission
- The European research community, represented by the EOSC Association
- EU countries and countries associated with Horizon Europe, represented through a Steering Board to be set up in 2021 outside of the EOSC Association

The European Commission is providing financial support to implement the EOSC by means of projects under the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (Horizon 2020). Also, EU countries and countries associated with Horizon 2020, represented in the EOSC Governance Board, agreed unanimously to run the EOSC as a co-programmed European Partnership under Horizon Europe from 2021. The number of Horizon 2020 projects contributing to EOSC reached over 50 by 2021².

¹https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/new_paper_d_-_list_of_provisional_members_and_observers_no_cover.pdf

² EOSC Projects: <https://eosc-portal.eu/about/eosc-projects>

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Two of the H2020 flagship EOSC projects, EOSC-hub and OpenAIRE-Advance, in collaboration with other EOSC projects of the past (EOSCpilot, eInfraCentral), established the central services of EOSC by November 2018. The EOSC Portal is currently operated by the EOSC Enhance and EOSC projects funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. EOSC Enhance is a 2 years CSA project, which aims at providing a bridge between the flagships projects and the EOSC Future and developing the EOSC portal and the functionalities for the researchers and the providers. The EOSC Future started in April 2021, will run for 3 years and provide the next flagship projects for the development of the core services of the EOSC portal. Along with EOSC Future, there are a number of other projects started in 2020 and 2021, which will provide additional thematic and regional services to the EOSC Ecosystem. These projects and the providers they bring in, comprise the EOSC Exchange, i.e., the set of providers who will integrate and be interoperable with the core EOSC services that EOSC Future will deliver.

The core EOSC services deliver a toolkit of extensible and reusable services, serving both the supply and demand side, such as a catalogue of services, a marketplace of services, software and datasets, monitoring and accounting services, helpdesk services, and finally AAI services. These core services build on mature processes, policies and tools from the leading European federated e-Infrastructures to cover the whole life-cycle of services, from planning to delivery. The catalogue aggregates services from local, regional and national e-Infrastructures in Europe, Africa, Asia, Canada and South America.

Services are exposed to the public (both providers, users and supporters) via the EOSC Portal, which acts as a single contact point to discover, access, use and reuse a broad spectrum of resources for advanced data-driven research. Through the virtual access mechanism, more scientific communities and users have access to services supporting their scientific discovery and collaboration across disciplinary and geographical boundaries.

Our EOSC integration plan is based on the current capabilities and possibilities of the EOSC Portal and its back-end. However, we are aware that the EOSC landscape is evolving:

- The 'EOSC Core' is under definition by the EOSC Future, with milestones for releases expected at the end of September 2021 and next in September 2022. The EOSC Core will be the simplest set of services and interfaces that are required for EOSC to function. We expect that the EOSC Portal, Marketplace, and those federation services that are considered for use (see Section 6) will remain part of the EOSC Core, and therefore will stay relevant for NEANIAS.
- Six (6) Horizon2020 calls, titled '*INFRAEOSC-07-2020 Increasing the service offer of the EOSC Portal*', were closed on June 18, 2020. The projects, which started in January 2021, will bring into EOSC (or continue to operate in EOSC) a diverse set of services from the following areas:
 - Distributed and cloud computing resources
 - Data services
 - Services supporting scholarly communication and open access

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- Above the net services (range from simple tools to complex collaborative platforms, including real-time communications and media)
- Services and resources from non-research public sector data providers
- Additional research enabling services (text and data mining or Copernicus services)

The projects are expected to cover, to a large extent, research management services that are considered for integration in Section 6, or additional services that can be considered in the future.

3. Integration guidelines for EOSC

This section is written based on the integration guidelines that exist on the EOSC Portal in August 2021³. The document explains the compulsory and the optional steps that service providers need to take to become service providers in EOSC.

3.1. Overview of integration approaches

The minimum level of EOSC integration is that the service entry should be published in the EOSC Portal and Marketplace. Publication of a service entry ensures that the service meets minimum requirements, is visible, properly described and accessible for new users. If the service requires users to apply for access, then such user access requests will be submitted via the EOSC Marketplace, then forwarded to the service provider who can evaluate and respond to the requests using the EOSC tools. The service publication is elaborated in Section 3.2.

Additional integration options also exist besides the portal publication, but all those integrations are optional. A provider is free to choose from these additional integration options according to the value seen for the users from these additional ties with EOSC. These additional options are described in Section 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5.

Our intended use of the compulsory publication step, as well as the optional steps are described in Section 6.

3.2. Registering in the EOSC portal

EOSC services can be accessed by users via the EOSC Portal. The registration of a service to EOSC follows an approach consisting of 3 Phases⁴ as shown in the figure below:

- Phase A: Registration of Authorized Representative of Provider
- Phase B: Onboarding of EOSC Provider
- Phase C: Registration of resource

³ <https://eosc-portal.eu/for-providers>

⁴ EOSC Provider and Resource Onboarding Tutorial, v1.00 – 30/09/2020, <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-provider-portal-basic-guide>

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Figure 3.1. Main Onboarding Process

The phases are further detailed into stages as follows:

1. The ARP⁵ registers with the EOSC Portal
2. The AARP⁶ logins to the EOSC Portal
3. The AARP asserts Authorisation for the Provider
4. The AARP applies to onboard the Provider
5. The EPOT⁷ reviews the Provider Profile
6. The AARP selects the method to onboard Resources
7. The AARP applies to onboard Resources
8. The EPOT reviews the Resource Profiles
9. The AARP applies to onboard other Resources
10. The EPQT⁸ creates a Report

In simple terms, for onboarding a service to the EOSC portal, the service provider shall first identify the person, who will assume all tasks related to the registration of the provider on EOSC, and thus will act as the Authorised Representative of the Provider in what EOSC is concerned. This person, after being properly authenticated on EOSC portal, needs to fill-in

⁵ ARP: Authorised Representative of the Provider

⁶ AARP: Authorised and Authenticated Representative of the Provider

⁷ EPOT: EOSC Portal Onboarding Team

⁸ EPQT: EOSC Portal Quality Team

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some information on the provider's organization in order to register the provider on EOSC. When this information, which comprises the Provider Profile on EOSC, is reviewed and validated by the EOSC Portal Onboarding Team, the representative of the provider may continue with onboarding Resources (i.e. Services) on EOSC, by completing another standardised form called Resource Profile. The Resource Profile covers more detailed information which enables the EOSC Portal Onboarding Team to determine that the service fulfils all requirements of the 'Rules of Participation' in addition to information needed to populate the EOSC Service Portfolio entry corresponding to the new service. The Resource Profile is a longer form, requesting information about a service in the following categories:

- **Basic Information:** ID, Name, Resource Organisation, Resource Providers, Webpage
- **Marketing Information:** Description, Tagline, Logo, Multimedia, Use Cases
- **Classification Information:** Scientific Domain and Subdomain, Category and Subcategory, Target Users, Access Type and Mode, Tags
- **Geographical and Language Availability Information**
- **Resource Location Information:** information about the Geographic Location a service is hosted or deployed (including the data processed by the service).
- **Contact Information for:**
 - Main Contact/Resource Owner and Public Contact: Name, Email, Phone, Position, Organisation
 - Other Contacts: Helpdesk Email, Security Contact Email
- **Maturity Information:** Technology Readiness Level, Life Cycle Status, Certifications, Standards, Open Source Technologies, Version, Last Update, Change Log
- **Dependencies Information:** Required Resources, Related Resources, Related Platforms
- **Attribution Information:** Funding Body, Funding Program, Grant/Project Name
- **Management Information:** Helpdesk Page, User Manual, Terms Of Use, Privacy Policy, Access Policy, Service Level, Training Information, Status Monitoring, Maintenance
- **Access and Order Information:** Order Type, Order
- **Financial Information:** Payment Model, Pricing

The submitted information is reviewed for suitability by the EOSC Portal Quality Team and upon its successful validation, the resource (service) is made public and accessible on the EOSC Portal and Marketplace.

This process is continuously evolving and new sets of rules and criteria are being examined and introduced by EOSC.

3.2.1. EOSC fundamental service requirements

At the time of writing, there are the following fundamental requirements for a service to be onboarded in EOSC:

1. The service falls within the remit of the EOSC activities, i.e. it brings value to users and facilitates them to implement Open Science.

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2. It is either an online service (e.g. a web application portal, a web service) or a 'human' service, such as training and consultancy. (Plain datasets and software artefacts should not be directly onboarded to EOSC. There are other ways to do that.)
3. The service is mature, reaching 'Technology Readiness Level 7 (TRL7). TRL7 services are 'System prototype demonstration in operational environment', practically meaning that they have been already used by early adopter scientists.
4. The compulsory fields of the service description template are filled during onboarding.

3.3. Integrating with federation services

EOSC offers a set of services that service providers can use to enhance their services from the operational perspective. These services can, for example, simplify how users access the service via federated authentication, they can improve service reliability, they can provide details on capacity consumption by the users, or can simplify user interaction via a helpdesk. This section provides an overview of these services, using the same structure for each, under the perspective of EOSC, considering relevance to NEANIAS. In section 5.2 we elaborate further on the perspective of NEANIAS for integration.

3.3.1. Federated user authentication and authorisation

3.3.1.1. Rationale and Relevance to NEANIAS

The EOSC Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) [25] is among the pillars of EOSC architecture as it is of relevance to almost every service in EOSC landscape as it sets the facilities and framework for accounted or otherwise controlled access to resources. Thus, any service that needs to restrict access to resources due to access policies that may span from free to restricted access, or simply wants to track usage of those resources, can make use of EOSC AAI.

In NEANIAS, federated user authentication and authorization is among the fundamental EOSC services to integrate with.

3.3.1.2. Description

The EOSC Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) seeks to enable seamless, authenticated access to services and research data in EOSC. The EOSC AAI facilitates service providers to control access to their services from users holding identities (usernames and passwords or other credentials) from a very broad set of academic, community or social Identity Providers (IdPs). The EOSC AAI brings together these IdPs, the EOSC service providers (SPs) and intermediary identity management proxies into a single, interoperable infrastructure. The EOSC AAI builds on open standards including SAML 2.0, OpenID Connect, OAuth 2.0 and X.509v3 to offer a flexible framework for access management. The EOSC AAI comprises different, compatible endpoint services, namely B2ACCESS, Check-in, eduTEAMS and INDIGO-IAM that service providers are free to choose from depending on their preference of technology or provider. The infrastructure also includes Perun, a component that can be used for managing users' access rights to the services, and a set of Token Translation Services to translate between different protocols or technologies when passing identities and user roles to services.

3.3.2. Availability and reliability monitoring

3.3.2.1. Rationale and Relevance to NEANIAS

The monitoring service is an essential instrument for understanding the quality of service offerings, both from the consumer (user) perspective, but also from the provider (service owner) perspective: the former can understand aspects of the reliability of the service, while the latter can be informed to improve it and respond to relevant incidents. Having a 3rd party monitoring service is relevant to almost all service providers as it offers an objective measure of specific performance characteristics.

Monitoring is of relevance to most NEANIAS services and is targeted by integration activities for services that are onboarding EOSC.

3.3.2.2. Description

Monitoring is the key service needed to gain insights into an infrastructure. It needs to be continuous and on-demand to quickly detect, correlate, and analyse data for a fast reaction to anomalous behaviour. The challenge of this type of monitoring is how to quickly identify and correlate problems before they affect end-users and ultimately the productivity of their organizations. The features of a monitoring system are monitoring of services, reporting availability and reliability, visualization of the services status, providing dashboard interfaces and sending real-time alerts. Management teams, administrators, service owners can monitor the availability and reliability of the services from a high-level view down to individual system metrics and monitor the conformance of multiple SLAs.

In EOSC the following monitoring services can be found:

- EGI Service Monitoring [17] is an infrastructure monitoring service which relies on data generated by functional probes. The features of the EGI Service Monitoring include:
 - Minimal development effort for setting up monitoring services
 - Read-to-use user interface
 - Automated reporting tools
- PerfSONAR [18] is a network monitoring service aimed at the research and education community. It is based on an open-source, modular and flexible architecture, which accounts for the complexity of network infrastructures. The features of the PerfSONAR service include:
 - a dashboard, which reports matrices of worldwide network monitoring measurements
 - uniform interfaces for data retrieval and uniform measurements formats
 - user-defined scheduled measurements
 - on-demand measurements
- Although ARGO monitoring [19] at the time of writing is not available as a federated EOSC service, it is currently employed for the monitoring of the EOSC Portal. The ARGO monitoring and alerting service provides the following features:
 - Open source modular architecture
 - Horizontal scalability
 - Scalable elaboration of metrics

The ARGO service collects status results from one or more monitoring engine(s) and delivers status results and/or monthly availability (A) and reliability (R) results of

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distributed services. Both status results and A/R metrics are presented through a Web UI, with the ability for a user to drill-down from the availability of a site to individual services, to individual test results that contributed to the computed figure. ARGO is also capable to send notifications to the service administrators in case of a failure/warning on one of the services monitored.

3.3.3. Usage accounting

3.3.3.1. Rationale and Relevance to NEANIAS

Usage Accounting is an instrument that allows service providers and consequently users, to monitor the use of resources in the infrastructure.

Usage Accounting is of great relevance to NEANIAS services, however the substantially different requirements of most services and regulatory challenges restrict the usability of existing EOSC offerings for their needs.

3.3.3.2. Description

EGI provides an accounting service [10] for EOSC. EGI accounting stores user accounting records from various services, such as Cloud, HPC and storage usage. It works thanks to a network of message brokers that transfer usage data from the host to a central repository of information. The data is handled securely and can be consulted online through the EGI Accounting Portal [11]. EGI accounting provides:

- Increased control over resource consumption
- Reduced overhead of defining data models, architecture, and setup of an accounting system
- Reduced cost of maintaining an accounting infrastructure
- Access to a reliable, high available, high-performance service
- User friendly web interface

This accounting service can collect, store, aggregate, and display usage information about the following types of services:

- High Throughput Compute
- Infrastructure-as-a-Service cloud virtual machines
- Storage space providers
- Data set providers

The usage data is collected from those Resource Centres that provide the above types of services, and that connect their service endpoints to the centrally managed Accounting Service. Accounting information is gathered from the service by probes and sensors according to certain data formats.

Probes and sensors are deployed locally at the service providers. Data is forwarded from the sensors into a central Accounting Repository where those data are processed to generate various summaries and views for display in the Accounting Portal. Depending on the complexity of the provider the accounting data may go via intermediate repositories that collate them for particular regions, sub-infrastructures or communities. EOSC service providers can either directly publish accounting information into the EOSC Accounting Repository or can do so via an intermediate repository that serves for example a specific

region or group of providers. It is up to the provider (group) to use the central repository directly, or to apply an intermediary accounting infrastructure and connect it to EOSC.

3.3.4. Helpdesk

3.3.4.1. Rationale and Relevance to NEANIAS

Helpdesk federation acts in the direction of improving user experience and confidence on EOSC registered services, as it guarantees to service consumers that there is a support “line” for a service in EOSC. As such it is important for any EOSC onboarded service to be integrated with the respective service.

Helpdesk integration is among the priorities of NEANIAS operations’ activities for EOSC services onboarding, but also covers almost all other NEANIAS services.

3.3.4.2. Description

The EOSC Helpdesk [13] is the entry point and ticketing system/request tracker for issues concerning EOSC services. New service providers of EOSC can integrate into the Helpdesk and this results in:

- a corresponding support topic listed on the Helpdesk user interface (for users to ask questions or raise issues directly to the provider)
- the provider support team to receive notifications about tickets that are assigned to this topic by the users, or by the ticket handler team of EOSC.

The Helpdesk therefore serves two groups, offering the following features to them:

- Main features offered to users:
 - Creation of a ticket for any of the EOSC Services
 - Display all the tickets created by the owner
 - Find previously created tickets
 - Receive notifications about answers and changes to the tickets
 - Login with the EOSC AAI system
- Main features offered to the provider Helpdesk Team:
 - Notification when a new ticket is created
 - Classification of the tickets
 - Escalation of the tickets to the ticket handler team of EOSC.
 - Creation of a new support unit with assignation of an administrator role to specific users
 - Management of incident or disruption of EOSC services
 - Interface for communicating with other service providers ticketing systems
 - First level support for EOSC integrated services as a service
 - Interface with a Known Errors Database and with a Change Management Database

EOSC services can use the EOSC Helpdesk choosing one of the following integration options:

1. Direct Usage: Use directly the EOSC helpdesk as the ticketing system for the service.
2. Ticket Redirection: Use the EOSC helpdesk only as a contact point to redirect the entry request for the specific service to a mailing list.
3. Full Integration: Integrate an external ticketing system with the EOSC helpdesk infrastructure to enable transfer of tickets between them.

3.4. Research data management

3.4.1. Rationale and Relevance to NEANIAS

Research Data Management (RDM) services offer a set of instruments that cover various stages of the lifecycle of Research Data, starting for the planning of their creation or reuse and reaching to the discovery and use by other researchers.

3.4.2. Description

EOSC offers various services (usually called horizontal services) for service providers to help them more easily manage research data and implement scenarios where research data (often 'big data') need to be stored, transferred, analysed, indexed, etc. Some of the typical situations where a service can benefit from such support:

- The service needs to store and analyse data with the use of external computing and storage resources (e.g. cloud resources)
- The service needs to copy/move big data between an organization's premises and other sites
- The service needs an external repository to deposit research data or scientific applications for broader sharing and reuse
- The service needs functionality to limit or allow access to authorized users

Figure 3.2. positions some relevant services that are made available by the EOSC Portal Catalogue & Marketplace along the 'virtuous cycle of research', showing how they can be used to

1. Discover existing research data and services/applications
2. Process and analyse digital research data
3. Archive and curate research data
4. Deposit and make available research data for reuse

These services, even if they are positioned within the same stage of the cycle, provide different features and/or are offered with different conditions of use. Additional steps in the cycle, such as research planning and verification, research training and dissemination (not shown for brevity), are also covered by horizontal services provided by EOSC via the EOSC Portal Catalogue & Marketplace⁹, along with high level information, on how a researcher can start using them (e.g., user guides and other relevant materials).

⁹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

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Figure 3.2. EOSC services to support the virtuous cycle of research

3.5. EOSC service management system

As part of the contribution to EOSC, the EOSC-hub project developed an IT Service Management system (SMS). The SMS ensures a robust and resilient service delivery in the EOSC federated infrastructure with different types of many-to-many relationships between users, providers, and clients.

What is IT Service Management?

The key idea behind IT service management could be summarized like this: By following a service-oriented approach, an IT organisation (which may be everything from an internal IT department over a shared IT unit up to an external IT provider) is able to better understand what they do and offer, and how this is aligned to the needs of their customers and users. IT service management (ITSM) refers to the entirety of activities – directed by policies, organized and structured in processes and supporting procedures – that are performed by an organization to design, plan, deliver, operate and control information technology (IT) services offered to customers. And by implementing IT service management processes, the activities carried out to plan, deliver, operate and control these services become more structured and repeatable, with clearly defined responsibilities. All this helps an IT organisation to increase their level of professionalism and organisational maturity.

The EOSC-hub SMS represents the entirety of activities performed by the providers that contribute to the EOSC core to plan, deliver, operate, and control the services offered to EOSC. The SMS also covers (to different extent) the activities of those service providers that have

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been onboarded to EOSC via the EOSC Portal. The activities carried out in the context of the SMS are structured and organised into processes and procedures according to the FitSM IT Management framework [30]. By defining requirements, the 14 processes of FitSM help service providers:

Process	Objective
Service portfolio management (SPM)	To define and maintain a service portfolio
Service level management (SLM)	To maintain a service catalogue, and to define, agree and monitor service levels with customers by establishing meaningful service level agreements (SLAs) and supportive operational level agreements (OLAs) and underpinning agreements (UAs) with suppliers
Service reporting management (SRM)	To specify all service reports and ensure they are produced according to specifications in a timely manner to support decision-making
Service availability and continuity management (SACM)	To ensure sufficient service availability to meet agreed requirements and adequate service continuity
Capacity management (CAPM)	To ensure sufficient capacities are provided to meet agreed service capacity and performance requirements
Information security management (ISM)	To manage information security effectively through all activities performed to deliver and manage services, so that the confidentiality, integrity and accessibility of relevant information are preserved
Customer relationship management (CRM)	To establish and maintain a good relationship with customers receiving services
Supplier relationship management (SUPPM)	To establish and maintain a healthy relationship with suppliers supporting the service provider in delivering services to customers, and monitor their performance
Incident and service request management (ISRM)	To restore normal / agreed service operation within the agreed time after the occurrence of an incident, and to respond to user service requests
Problem management (PM)	To investigate the root causes of (recurring) incidents in order to avoid future recurrence of incidents by resolving the underlying cause, or to ensure workarounds/temporary fixes are available
Configuration management (CONFM)	To provide and maintain a logical model of all configuration items (CIs) and their relationships and dependencies

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Change management (CHM)	To ensure changes to CIs are planned, approved, implemented and reviewed in a controlled manner to avoid adverse impact of changes to services or the customers receiving services
Release and deployment management (RDM)	To bundle changes of one or more CIs to releases, so that these changes can be tested and deployed to the live environment together
Continual service improvement management (CSI)	To identify, prioritize, plan, implement and review improvements to services and service management

For each of these processes, as well as for certain general aspects in the context of ITSM, FitSM (within the FitSM-1 document) defines a small number of implementation requirements, while the FitSM-2 document provides guidelines on the activities to set up and implement ITSM using these processes. The FitSM-3 document describes the proposed roles to be assigned to execute the ITSM processes as part of a service management system.

4. NEANIAS services to be integrated to EOSC

The following section introduces the NEANIAS services that will be integrated into EOSC. These services will cover three major research sectors; Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. Beyond these thematic services, NEANIAS develops/provides Core services in four (4) groups; C1 covers Open-Science lifecycle support services, while C2 covers EOSC hub, RIs and cloud integration enabling services, C3 covers AI and C4 covers Visualization services. C1 and C2 provide basic services to enable integration of the thematic services in NEANIAS, i.e. not services targeting reuse by 3rd parties, therefore they will not be onboarded to EOSC and as such they are not presented in detail in this section. On the other hand, the C3 and C4 services support the delivery of NEANIAS thematic services, and their integration to EOSC is optional, based on the plans of the respective providers, which are described in Section 6.

4.1. Underwater services

Underwater surveys have numerous scientific and commercial applications in the fields of archaeology, geology, biology, and energy involving tasks such as ancient shipwreck prospection, ecological studies, environmental damage assessment, and detection of temporal changes. More specifically, this is a significant easier entry point for the targeted users/customers going from raw data (U1) to maps, aided by an agile and fit-for-purpose service, allowing them to create higher resolution maps compared to DTMs shared by initiatives like EMODNET and GEBCO. Moreover, scientists and marine operations companies can benefit from acquired images as they provide, from the cognitive point of view (U2), the most precise and accurate representation of the areas surveyed, enabling a detailed analysis of the structures of interest. In addition, the novel seabed classification service (U3) engages specific user-communities through the foreseen demonstrations in several underwater datasets addressing current needs of archaeologists, submarine volcano/geohazards, energy power cabling planners and oil & gas engineers.

4.1.1. U1 - Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data

The UW-BAT (Bathyprocessing) service provides a large number of MB-System tools to post-process vendor specific raw data. Its approach is to create digital terrain models (DTM) and maps from multibeam echosounder (MBES) raw data.

4.1.2. U2 - Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data

The Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data (UW-MOS) service deals with optical mapping in underwater environments. UW-MOS provides an operational solution for large area representation of the seafloor addressing also visibility limitations from the underwater medium.

4.1.3. U3 - Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data

The Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data service delivers a user-friendly cloud-based solution integrating cutting-edge machine learning frameworks for mapping several seabed classes, validated for archaeological, geo-hazards, energy, and other applications.

4.2. Atmosphere services

In the novel A1 service, although algorithms may be commercially available, no algorithms are standardized and widely accepted by the scientific and regulatory communities, raising a

significant business opportunity since A1 allows currently missing regularization perspectives. The novel A2 service engages geohazard scientific and government public protection authorities towards delivering timely alerts on forecasting geohazards activities. For seismic/volcanic hazards, several exploitation opportunities will be raised, also from providing to stakeholders the crucial information of how gas and particulate concentrations change in space and time. The innovative A3 service engages users and leverages business exploitation opportunities in (i) agriculture since air quality influences the agricultural productivity (ii) urban-related studies including planning, land use, and real-estate (iii) in insurance/ health since e.g. preventive measures in hospitals/ pharmacies can respond to citizens' needs.

4.2.1.A1 - Greenhouse Gases Flux Density Monitoring

The Greenhouse Gases Flux Density Monitoring (ATMO-FLUD) service provides a set of algorithms for the calculation of flux densities of Sensible Heat, Latent Heat, Turbulent Kinetic Energy and other scalars like GHGs. The input data to the service is user provided although test data are available for trial runs. Real data should be experimentally obtained by the user bearing in mind that the fundamental method employed in this service is the "Eddy Covariance".

4.2.2.A2 - Monitor atmospheric Perturbations and Components in Active Tectonic Regions

A2 service consists of two sub-services; the ATMO-SEISM and the ATMO-STRESS services.

ATMO-SEISM is a service for scientists to design, develop and test the correlation between gas measurements, atmospheric conditions and earthquake data. The considered earthquake parameters are: the earthquake Magnitude, the distance between the hypocentre and the gas emission site, and data and time of the seismic event. This service is focused especially on radon, but it could be possibly used also for other gases emitted in volcanic areas, like SO₂ and CO₂. The language that is used is Python, one of the most popular languages in data science. Jupyter Hub is a multi-user development environment using the IPython interface, allowing code implementation and interpretation using a web interface.

ATMO-STRESS shows regional trends on 2-D gridded map (x-y plane) and can reconstruct a paleostress trajectory map by implementing the following two different methods (Lee and Angelier, 1993): (i) polynomial and (ii) distance weighted interpolation. It represents an upgrade of the already existing "Lissage" program (Lee and Angelier, 1994), which presented several limitations: it has been written using the Turbo C language, it is not user-friendly, it does not consider different data sources, and it cannot manage a large amount of data. All these issues are overcome thanks to ATMO-STRESS service, which also allows to download output maps in formats compatible with GIS environments (e.g. shp, kml)

4.2.3.A3 - Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting

The Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting (ATMO-4CAST) service allows the generation of meteorological forecasts by using the Weather Research and Forecast Model. For this forecast computation, it is expected that the users provide relevant meteorological data. An example of such an input file is provided in the service web page. The service results are files, downloadable in different formats for a more custom analysis and PDF files for a preliminary graphical visualisation.

4.3. Space services

The Space services deliver a springboard of tools to enrich the workflows of a wide range of targeted users from academic/research institutions to industrial stakeholders, e.g. aerospace engineering and related technology companies, but also national space agencies and public outreach bodies, e.g. space museums and planetariums.

The latest NEANIAS release includes seven services tailored to the Space sector user requirements and driven by three clusters of common functionalities, i.e.: S1 - FAIR Data Management and visualization for complex data and metadata, S2- Map making and mosaicing for multidimensional images, S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques.

S1, namely “SPACE-VIS” services, provide required functionalities that enable efficient and scalable visual discovery, exposed through advanced interaction paradigms, such as the visual analytic, also exploiting virtual reality starting from software modules such as the ViaLactea framework, Astra Data Navigator and the ADAM platform. S2, namely “SPACE-MOS” services, deliver multi-dimensional space maps through novel mosaicing techniques (i.e. stitching of multidimensional images/maps with overlapping fields of view) to a variety of prospective users/customers (e.g., mining & robotic engineers, mobile telecommunications, space scientists) starting from software modules such as Montage, ISIS3, ASP and the ADAM Data Processing System. S3, namely “SPACE-ML” services, deliver structure detection capabilities addressing the researchers’ needs to identify and classify, in an efficient way, specific structures of interest starting from software modules such as CAESAR, CUTEX, VLFF and well-known machine learning and deep learning algorithms and methods.

4.3.1. S1 - FAIR Data Management and Visualization for Complex Data and Metadata

The Space environment shares different needs ranging from management of complex datasets, scientific visualization, visual analytics including combining data analytics and mining with visualization also exposing outputs within advanced interaction environments using virtual and augmented reality. The developed tools and services in Space are tailored to 2D and 3D model computation, visualization and virtual reality navigation applications, and is underpinned by FAIR principles. In fact the S1 services optimize data discovery by the publication of outputs through the IVOA framework, which is in very wide use by the astronomical community and is increasingly being adopted by the planetary community following the EuroPlanet, VESPA and PlanMap initiatives. Data accessibility is guaranteed through deployment of standard protocols and interfaces implemented by the IVOA TAP and EPN-TAP protocols and the REST interface.

The ViaLactea service access astrophysical surveys to aid understanding of the star formation process of the Milky Way. ViaLactea Visual Analytics (VLVA) combine different types of visualization to perform analysis by exploring correlations managed in the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB). VLKB includes 2D and 3D (velocity cubes) surveys, numerical model outputs, point-like and diffuse object catalogues and allows for retrieval of all available datasets as well as cutouts on the positional and/or velocity axis. The Astra Data Navigator (ADN) is a virtual reality environment for visualizing large stellar catalogues and has been customised to access cloud services for interactive data exploration and navigation.

Finally, the Advanced Geospatial Data Management platform (ADAM) accesses a large variety of environmental data and is customised in NEANIAS to access planetary data provided by PlanetServer.

4.3.2. S2 - Map making and mosaicing for multidimensional image

Space science requires services for making high quality images from the raw data captured by instruments (map making) and for assembling those images into custom mosaics (mosaicing). There are some tools available for the community that are in TRL6 and are being ported to the EOSC, optimizing the specific features as needed by the relevant scientific groups. Concerning radioastronomy data, interferometric observations, due to the peculiarities of data acquisition, the service will take into account primary beam effects as a weight for data to be mosaiced. Planetary mapping requires high image quality so that individual data products/granule are co-registered to achieve iteratively cartographic description (e.g. geologic) of a planetary surface. To achieve mapping there is need for higher-level products, that are made accessible (high-level data are not always available on public space agency archives, such as PDS/PSA) and co-registered, mosaiced as needed.

The service exploits Montage and is integrated with VLKB (see 4.3.1) for merging adjacent datasets. The service also allows integration with data processing pipelines in ADAM which offers tools for planetary data analysis and for producing cartographic products, such as Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) and 3D models from stereo imagery.

4.3.3. S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques

The currently experienced dramatic increases of Space data volumes make automatic structure detection a necessity. This need will become more and more important due to the continuous increase of data volumes that will need to be analysed. Recently project partners were involved in projects for automatic structure recognition such as FP7 ViaLactea project and SKA precursor activities. CAESAR [22] is a software tool for extraction and parameterization of both compact and extended sources present in astronomical maps. CuTEX [23] analyses images in the infrared bands and, in particular, it was designed to resolve problems concerning the study of star forming regions. Planetary exploration missions have the constant need for terrain characterization, largely based on orbital remote sensing data. S3 service exploits these existing TRL6 software to perform pattern and structure detection in astronomical surveys as well as in planetary surface composition, topography and morphometry. The service also integrates cutting-edge machine learning algorithms, adopting pre-trained convolutional neural-networks for computer vision tasks (e.g. recognition, segmentation) adapted to the project-specific tasks by means of transfer learning approaches, to perform advanced classification for structures of sources in the sky or planetary surfaces to identify regions of interest.

4.4. C3 Artificial Intelligence services

C3 Artificial Intelligence services form the upper level of core services in the NEANIAS ecosystem and provide facilities that may reach up to the end user offering features of a typical Machine Learning (ML) workflow lifecycle, and that are also intended for composition of higher-level services. In this subsection, the overall role of C3 services in NEANIAS is presented. The EOSC integration of the C3 services is optional; current integration plans are presented in Section 6.

4.4.1. C3.1 AI Science Gateway: service for development of ML models using Jupyter Hub

A development environment is necessary for the researchers to design, prototype, implement and test AI powered solutions. To serve as a universal core service for multiple users, the popular IPython based Jupyter Hub project is preferred, with TensorFlow and Keras libraries. Researchers are able to prototype solutions, while computationally intense training can be loaded to a computational cluster. Results can be visualized using the Visualization gateway (C4.2).

4.4.2. C3.2 Serving trained ML models

Accessing trained models as web services should be possible seamlessly, with low efforts. To deploy a model as an API, large amount of memory is necessarily allocated and used constantly. Technically, there are multiple approaches to implement model serving, user and researcher-friendliness is prioritized.

The fundamental idea behind model serving is that authorized clients are able to access prediction functionality without directly accessing the model, which would create a serious overhead caused by data transfer and memory allocation. Instead, a RESTful API based communication is preferred between a model server and the client. The server implements the model, allocates memory to efficiently handle prediction, and listens for input parameters on the interface. On request, prediction is done using the inner implementation, and the results are responded to the client.

4.4.3. C3.3 Distributed Multi-GPU training of large ML models using Horovod

The training of deep neural networks on large amount of data requires a significant amount of processing time, which could be reduced by using GPU accelerators. The next step in increasing the performance is by using multiple GPU-enabled nodes in a distributed environment. While the parallel processing of deep neural networks has its limitations, Horovod [12] is a robust tool which can be used to scale the training of TensorFlow based network implementations.

4.4.4. C3.4 Distributed Machine Learning using SparkML

In addition to models based on neural networks (that can benefit from a multi-GPU deployment, especially for learning phases) that are managed through C3.3, other AI techniques for classification, regression, or clustering tasks can however benefit from a deployment and execution in a distributed and memory-based architecture such as the one offered by Spark. In particular, C3.4 will support a variety of machine learning models such as Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees and ensemble models (Random Forests and Gradient Boosting) for both classification and regression, clustering algorithms, and other support functions that are useful in real-world, large scale, machine learning pipelines. The set of basic ML algorithms and models can also be extended by means of creative parallel computing approaches (e.g. parallel implementations of DBSCAN algorithm on top of Spark, an algorithm which is not natively provided by MLib, are known and available).

4.5. C4 Visualisation services

C4 services, namely “visualisation services”, in the context of NEANIAS, form the upper level of core services in the NEANIAS ecosystem and provide facilities that may reach up to the end

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user offering features of a typical visualisation workflow lifecycle, and that are also intended for composition of higher level services.

In this subsection, the overall role of C4 services in NEANIAS is presented. The EOSC integration of the C4 services is optional; current integration plans are presented in Section 6.

4.5.1. C4.1 Framework for Visual Discovery (VD)

C4.1 provides tools to support data intensive computing for visual scientific discovery (including research training and outreach) for observational data, theoretical simulations and 2D/3D tiling and maps. C4.1 consists of three distinct high-performance services for visual analytics from multidimensional data tables (VD-VisIVO), high-quality volume rendering of particle-based datasets exploiting a variety of parallel programming models leveraging upon heterogeneous infrastructures (VD-Splotch) and creation of interactive 2D/3D tilings and maps (VD-Maps).

4.5.2. C4.2 Visualisation Gateway (VG)

C4.2 provides a development environment for designing, rapid prototyping, implementing and fully testing complex visualisation solutions for realising common data exploration workflows. To serve as a universal core service for multiple users, the popular IPython based Jupyter Hub project has been selected. C4.2 is built upon this and the framework for visual discovery developed in C4.1. C4.2 services are envisaged to be interconnected with C3.1 to visualise AI powered solutions, C4.3 to underpin powerful VR/AR solutions and C4.4 to facilitate end-user data accessibility. C4.2 services are deployed in a way that is fully embedded within the relevant workflows of end-user activities, while exploiting diverse parallelisation models and infrastructure accelerator capabilities.

4.5.3. C4.3 Toolkit for Cross Realities (XR)

C4.3 provides a toolkit underpinning an environment for designing, implementing and testing complex visualisation solutions exposed to end-users via Cross Realities (XR) mechanisms, e.g. those based on Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). To serve as a universal core service for multiple users, popular software frameworks and technologies have been selected based on a set of components used by an existing TLR6 software solution called Astro Data Navigator (ADN), e.g. the frameworks provided by the game engine Unity and HTC Vive headset. Such components support interactive data exploration and navigation mechanisms e.g. for advanced comparisons in multidimensional and multifrequency datasets for research and public outreach. C4.3 services are built upon extending components with a focus on providing services with enhanced realism, precision and usability along a number of aspects relating to enriched user experiences covering e.g. novel navigation mechanisms, advanced real-time tracking, VR/AR technologies and seamless integration of large-scale catalogues. C4.3 exploits the framework for visual discovery developed in C4.1. C4.3 services are envisaged to be interconnected seamlessly with C4.2 to furnish complex visualisation workflows and C4.4 to underpin advanced data access. The components identified so far are a data connector for retrieving, in a generic way, data coming from different sources (individual files or databases) and a positioning manager providing the capabilities to retrieve specific data about position/rotation of particular objects for specific temporal instants. The implementation of the later is envisaged to deploy cloud infrastructures to extract the relevant information through Spice kernels. As part of the XR toolkit various VR/AR viewers

are expected to be realised visualising not only space objects but also 3D data of various typologies of interest to other NEANIAS domains (e.g. atmospheric).

4.5.4. C4.4 Spatial Data Stores (DS)

Spatial data stores allow data to be referenced, query and retrieved, based on a given location (e.g. the globe, the Earth, planetary bodies with a proper reference system or the sky).

Earth Observation data, including Copernicus datasets and products, are referenced in the ADAM Data Access System (DAS), a software module that manages a large variety of geospatial information that feature different data format, geographic / geometric and time resolution. It allows accessing, visualizing, sub-setting, combining, processing, downloading all data sources simultaneously. The DAS exposes OGC Open Search and Web Coverage Service (WCS 2.x) interfaces that allow discovering available datasets and subset them in any dimension with a single query.

Planetary bodies differ from the sky on their concavity and dimensions, bodies being concave surfaces of limited sizes whereas the sky is convex and limitless. A coordinate reference system at the interface layer on spatial data bases is responsible to translate user requests in to internal data reference.

4.6. Identified requirements/interfaces

Based on the investigation of the services listed above, we identified the following services/support as requirements to integrate the thematic services to EOSC:

- Providers and Service modelling based on EOSC Provider and Resource profiles. This choice aims to facilitate the onboarding of NEANIAS providers and services in the EOSC portal, complying with the existing standards and EOSC guidelines.
- Authentication and authorization
- Monitoring
- Accounting – As described, the EOSC offered Usage Accounting Service primarily focuses on infrastructure level assets and services. The NEANIAS approach to the task, through the NEANIAS Accounting Service takes a more fine-grained approach, letting individual services define their own accountable resources and respective actions.
- Helpdesk – The Helpdesk requirements for the NEANIAS service offerings are addressed through the NEANIAS offered Helpdesk functionality under the Service Management System (SMS) defined processes and tools. Still, the approach taken is chosen so that future integrations with the EOSC Helpdesk remains an option.
- Data Management Planning
- Data Catalogue

In the next section, we intend to introduce the available EOSC services in these categories and how and to what extent they will be integrated with NEANIAS services.

5. Targeted EOSC Services for Integration

In this section, existing EOSC services, which could be used and integrated with the NEANIAS services, are introduced. These services have been selected based on integration requirements of EOSC, considering the specific needs of the NEANIAS thematic services. We aim to onboard the NEANIAS thematic services in EOSC (i.e. publishing them in the EOSC Portal), and we wish to expand their capabilities with the use of the EOSC-hub federation services, and some of the Research Data Management services. The next subsections provide an overview of these specific services.

5.1. EOSC Portal

NEANIAS aims to deliver thematic services to researchers via EOSC, therefore the registration of these services in the EOSC Portal is a compulsory step. The EOSC portal is the European Open Science Cloud gateway offering researchers the ability to discover, access and compare EOSC services and resources. The EOSC portal provides access to all researchers from all domains and is open to scientific users and service providers.

The EOSC portal brings together services and resources such as computing, storage, data management, networking, research publications and software from national and international research infrastructures, organizations and more. The EOSC portal Catalogue and Marketplace give researchers the ability to:

- Browse, search and discover a variety of services and resources
- Compare different services
- Access the services selected easily with existing credentials from a very broad set of academic, community or social identity providers
- Find out detailed information on each service including access policies, maturity level, latest updates, country availability, languages supported and more.
- Receive help and support for all services
- Write reviews for all services

Providers of services are able to contribute their services and resources to the EOSC portal, following the onboarding process presented in Section 3.2 of this document.

5.2. Federation Services

In this subsection, existing EOSC federation services, which we plan to directly integrate with the NEANIAS services or have been thoroughly taken into account in order to achieve future integration, are introduced.

5.2.1. AAI services

The NEANIAS project includes in its offering the NEANIAS AAI service that offers a horizontal solution for all NEANIAS services to cover the common requirements of authenticated access, whether it comes in the form of a direct user request or as cross service invocations. The NEANIAS AAI service in its core supports identity federation through well-established standards and protocols, including Open ID Connect (OIDC) and SAML.

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Using these standards and protocols, the NEANIAS AAI service acts as an integration point with the EOSC Portal offered AAI. This integration will allow EOSC-trusted users to be offered access to NEANIAS resources. As the number of EOSC-trusted identity providers expands, the NEANIAS AAI will also expand its reach to a wider user base, regardless of the end user supporting Identity Provider.

This approach also allows the NEANIAS AAI service to extend the network of federation of supported identity providers, providing seamless authenticated access to trusted users via widely used and accepted standards.

5.2.2. Availability and reliability monitoring

Availability monitoring is a service where users and service providers can check the status of an EOSC service and get information about its availability and reliability in the selected time period.

NEANIAS is providing an availability monitoring instrument, in order to be able to verify its compliance to the intended Services SLA, by using both an internal monitoring infrastructure and integrating with the ARGO monitoring platform. At the time of writing this integration is ongoing in order to cover all the NEANIAS thematic services.

5.2.3. Accounting

As mentioned in 3.3.3, NEANIAS usage accounting perspective has a substantially different perspective than the one that EOSC main accounting offering covers. Furthermore, there are challenges pertaining to sensitive data management that substantially hinder the usability of a 3rd party service for tracking usage data.

Despite these two obstacles, EOSC accounting remains relevant, as the NEANIAS thematic services will consume storage and computing capacity from underlying provider(s). Having a full understanding of this use (e.g. on a per provider and per user basis) would help the project build the picture of its operational costs and plan sustainable business model for beyond the project lifetime. The EOSC Accounting system can be helpful here and may offer the required level of details about computing and storage use.

However, as already mentioned, accounting in NEANIAS spans largely other concepts rather than direct measurement of physical (or virtualized) resources. This, cumulatively considered with other challenges, steers NEANIAS to a different direction. More specifically, the challenges are:

- NEANIAS employs a service rather than an infrastructure provided perspective, which needs additional accounting concepts (e.g. rated API calls, logons, publication sets etc.).
- NEANIAS engages a number of infrastructure providers that employ substantially different infrastructures (that may be further abstractions of other lower level resources), technologies and policies. The integration of proxies may be neither feasible nor acceptable due to policies of those providers.
- Accounting requires that user data are passed to a 3rd party infrastructure. This requires additional user consents and provider considerations, as the General Data Protection Regulation comes into play in such scenarios.

Furthermore, NEANIAS, by definition, is not specifically targeting EOSC accounting integration, and its accounting mandate covers mainly project-specific KPIs.

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Towards usage accounting NEANIAS has defined a generic model and infrastructure in order to capture the diverse characteristics of its services and the perspectives of their owners. This allows services to support additional and more advanced policies for both regulating their usage as well as offering a larger variety of options to their financial sustainability modelling. This is aligned to latest EOSC calls service uptake perspective, where utilization of resources is only one aspect of many to measure the use of a service. The “virtual access” concept is defined by service specific needs. Furthermore, functionally, accounting in NEANIAS offers the arsenal for applying policies at service level, while the accounting service lifts the burden of offering the required level of aggregated data for that.

At present, the project shall proceed with the internal accounting solution approach and will continuously monitor the landscape for the potential future EOSC integration at the resource provider level or any higher one, upon resolution of the aforementioned challenges.

5.2.4. Helpdesk

To assist and support the end users of the NEANIAS offered Services, a ticketing system is made available, acting as the entry point for service consumers to report issues, incidents and requests in a structured fashion. This ticketing system, formally named “NEANIAS service management IT system”, is NEANIAS Helpdesk system and supports the collection of:

- Incident Reports - Unplanned disruption of operation in a service or service component, or degradation of service quality versus the expected or agreed service level or operational level.
- Service Requests - User request for information, advice, access to a service, etc.

The NEANIAS Helpdesk processes and functionality, as defined within the context of the Service Management System (Section 5.4), aim to cover the NEANIAS users’ needs for support and communication with the respective service providers.

Although not a mandate within the NEANIAS description of action, the opportunity to integrate the NEANIAS Helpdesk with the EOSC Helpdesk may be beneficiary for the end users in providing a more streamlined support experience. To this end, the following integration options offered from the EOSC Helpdesk can be investigated for future integration:

- Ticket Redirection: Use the EOSC helpdesk only as a contact point to redirect the entry request for the specific service to a mailing list.
- Full Integration: Integrate an external ticketing system with the EOSC helpdesk infrastructure to enable transfer of tickets between them.

NEANIAS has no specific mandate for its service providers with respect to ticketing, so each one of them may choose the ticketing option they wish to adopt. The requirement set by the project is that:

- Access is open to all users.
- SSO should be adopted.
- Metrics should be shared with the project in order to assess service quality.

Apart from the aforementioned options, NEANIAS is offering a ticketing system to all its services that covers those requirements.

5.3. Research Data Management

In this section we provide an overview of some of the existing EOSC services regarding FAIR data management that we opted to reuse and integrate, so that NEANIAS services are conformant with the Open Data Guidelines [2] and the FAIR principles [8]. As our project moves along and as the EOSC service portfolio expands we will also expand our view and will consider additional research data management services for integration.

5.3.1. ARGOS Data Management Plan tool

Argos [3] is an open and extensible EOSC service that simplifies the management, validation, monitoring and maintenance and of Data Management Plans. It is a service provided by OpenAIRE, contributed by NEANIAS in its validation stage. Argos allows actors (researchers, managers, supervisors, etc.) to create actionable DMPs that may be freely exchanged among infrastructures for carrying out specific aspects of the Data management process in accordance with the intentions and commitment of Data owners. To facilitate the adoption of the platform, NEANIAS has engaged OpenAIRE experts since the beginning of the project to provide support on the use of the platform both in live presentations and as web training.

Argos is based on OpenDMP [5] which is by itself a free and open-source software used for actionable machine Data Management Planning that closely follows RDA DMP WG developments and specifications [4].

In NEANIAS, we exclusively use Argos to maintain our Data Management plans, however no integration is planned with other RDM related service in the scope of the project.

5.3.2. Research Data Repository

NEANIAS handles data in its own resources for processing and integrates with well-known data repositories for obtaining data of relevance to its services. Those are handled by each specific thematic service provider. Currently there are no functional requirements that direct service providers to proceed to integration with specific EOSC repositories, however the overall intent of the project to empower Open Science and FAIR data, applies a uniform policy for all its services with respect to data publication.

Zenodo [6], an EOSC service, is the catch-all repository developed and maintained by CERN as part of the OpenAIRE project, in support of Open Science and FAIR principles. Zenodo's aim is to store all of its contents for the lifetime of the repository, providing free access to all metadata under the CC0 license (except for email addresses). Additionally, all metadata can be harvested via the OAI-PMH mechanism for repository interoperability [7]. Moreover, Zenodo offers a REST API [9] to allow applications to:

- a) upload and publish research outputs,
- b) search published records,
- c) upload and download files.

In NEANIAS, we opted to use Zenodo via its REST API for depositing all research product metadata, and for all open-access research data.

5.3.3. Research Data Catalogue

Data FAIRness requires that data are searchable by their audience, which in turn, requires that they are properly described and registered.

NEANIAS uses Zenodo as its data catalogue and follow the respective metadata description specification. Furthermore we will organize data under the "community" concept, in order to

facilitate their attribution to the project and simplify their discovery when coming from NEANIAS origins.

5.3.4. PID infrastructure

Publishing data requires that those can be identified uniquely by their consumers. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are the common construct for that. In NEANIAS, all published datasets will acquire a PID, under the DOI schema.

We use Zenodo as a Persistent Identifier (PID) production service, to allow NEANIAS services to automatically obtain PIDs for research outputs.

5.4. Service Management

As presented in Deliverable D8.2 “EOSC Service Model” [29], NEANIAS chose to develop an IT Service Management System of its own, which is nevertheless compatible with the EOSC one. More specifically, the NEANIAS SMS is developed based on the same service management framework as the EOSC one, i.e. FitSM, with ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018 extensions [31] (where/if needed), utilising also ITIL guidance [32] as best practice. This way, we aim on one hand to be compliant with the EOSC service management system and on the other hand to establish a more tailored-made SMS, which will better serve the needs of NEANIAS services. Additionally, we aim to have increased control on the SMS, so that we can adjust it more easily and quickly to future developments of the services and needs of the providers of NEANIAS services.

For the initial establishment of the NEANIAS service management system, 8 out of the 14 processes of the FitSM framework have been adopted. These processes, which focus on the visibility of the services, the interaction of NEANIAS with the users of its services, as well as on areas related to the enhancement/ improvement and troubleshooting of the services, are:

Table 1: NEANIAS service management processes

Process ID	Process title
SPM	Service portfolio management
SLM	Service level management
SRM	Service reporting management
CRM	Customer relationship management
ISRM	Incident and service request management
CHM	Change management
RDM	Release and deployment management

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CSI	Continual service improvement management
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The adoption of the remaining 6 processes of the FitSM framework by NEANIAS will be reconsidered in the future as service releases and the service management system itself mature, and new needs, which cannot be facilitated by the initial set of service management processes, arise.

The above service management processes are supported by the following procedures:

Table 2: NEANIAS service management procedures

Procedure ID	Procedure title
CRM1	Handling customer complaints
CRM2	Reviewing customer satisfaction
ISRM1	Handling Incidents & Service Requests
CHM1	Handling Changes
RDM1	Building and Deploying Releases
CSI1	Handling Improvements

The main tools that support the NEANIAS SMS include the following:

Tool	Functionality
NEANIAS catalogue portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides the interface to service providers to register and describe their services • Presents information about the services that NEANIAS provides to users • Enables service ordering • Provides the interface to users for submitting incidents and service requests, complaints, requirements about services, etc.
NEANIAS service management IT system ¹⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitors the lifecycle of incidents and service requests, complaints, changes, etc.
NEANIAS wiki	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system

¹⁰ The NEANIAS service management IT system is developed under WP7 and implements a workflow-type functionality on a ticketing software platform (redmine).

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The above tools are complemented by own tools of the thematic/core service providers, which focus on the more technical aspects of service management (e.g. performance monitoring, logging, event management, capacity management etc.).

6. Integration plan to EOSC

In this section we present the integration plan of NEANIAS services to EOSC as it has been updated by the time of writing this document, based on EOSC developments and the evolution of NEANIAS services. Our fundamental goals, as defined since the beginning of the project, are:

1. Publish NEANIAS thematic services in EOSC. Consider the publishing of additional NEANIAS services in EOSC in a future stage.
2. Integrate NEANIAS services (thematic and core) with relevant EOSC services, where we see value of the integration (e.g. to enhance our operations, to deliver more features to users).
3. Develop the NEANIAS IT Service Management System gradually, and in an EOSC compatible way.

We aim to achieve these goals following an agile approach that is based on successive development cycles, considering the following:

- The cycles bring NEANIAS services from very basic EOSC integration with minimal functionalities to more complex EOSC integration with advanced capabilities.
- We specify the exact content for each cycle considering the situation at that moment when we reach that cycle.
- The cycles can be repeated for the different Thematic Services independently from each other. For example, cycle 1 can start for the most mature Thematic service as soon as that thematic service is ready for publication in EOSC. Other thematic services will be considered for cycle 1 once they become mature enough for EOSC.
- Cycle 1 as well as cycle 2 has a set of preparatory steps that NEANIAS should complete before any of the thematic services reach those cycles. (These preparatory steps should be completed only one time, while the cycles should be completed one time for each thematic service.)

Preparatory steps for cycle 1 (done once):

- NEANIAS portal and services catalogue prototype deployment.
- NEANIAS service catalogue sign up and registration.
 - Providers' registration based on EOSC onboarding process.
 - NEANIAS services terms of use definition and acceptance based on EOSC RoP.
- Setup the NEANIAS IT Service Management skeleton where service management documentations can be developed and stored (to be defined by WP7).

Provisional timeline: Started at M3; Finish by M24.

The preparatory steps for cycle 1 have already been completed as:

- The NEANIAS catalogue portal has been developed, deployed, and populated with information on NEANIAS providers and services.
- Providers of NEANIAS services have been registered on NEANIAS catalogue portal, using EOSC Provider Profile metadata.

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- Terms of Use and Privacy Policy skeletons have been developed, in order to be reused and customized by each NEANIAS service during EOSC onboarding.
- The NEANIAS Service Management System has been defined in D8.2 [29].
- Tools supporting the operation of the NEANIAS Service Management System have been defined (see Section 5.4), and are continuously evolving according to the needs of the NEANIAS services.

Cycle 1 – Make NEANIAS thematic services accessible to EOSC users by following the EOSC onboarding process (done for each thematic service):

- Ensure EOSC RoP compliance (i.e. we are able to fill the EOSC Service Description Template for the NEANIAS thematic service which is in scope).
- Define NEANIAS services pricing as well as respective SLA(s) and OLA(s) for the service.
- Activate ordering (access requests) from the EOSC Portal to NEANIAS thematic services.
- Ensure EOSC access policies and licensing compliance.
- Enable single sign-on from the EOSC Portal to the NEANIAS Thematic service (through the NEANIAS AAI service).
- Provide minimum level documentation and helpdesk support for users.
- Ensure minimum level of user feedback collection and continuous improvement (CRM).

Provisional timeline: Start at M12; Finish by M31 (EOSC catalogue integration and AAI integration by M25 based on D6.1).

Cycle 1 activities are in progress for each thematic service independently and follow the maturity of each service.

Preparatory steps for cycle 2 (done once):

- Release the NEANIAS research product catalogue based on OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform.
- Release NEANIAS PID service based on OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform.
- Release the NEANIAS Data Validation Service.
- Release the NEANIAS Data Publishing Service.
- Integrate with OpenDMP deployed on OpenAIRE as Argos.

Cycle 2 – Enrich NEANIAS services with research product catalogue and data management capabilities (done for each thematic service):

- Integrate with the NEANIAS research product catalogue based on OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform.
- Integrate with NEANIAS PID service based on OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform.
- Integrate with the NEANIAS Data Validation Service.
- Integrate with the NEANIAS Data Publishing Service.
- Integrate with OpenDMP deployed on OpenAIRE as Argos.

Provisional timeline: Finish by M32.

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Cycle 2 activities are in progress for each thematic service independently, and follow the maturity of each service.

Cycle 3 – Improve support for EOSC users based on initial experiences (done for each thematic service):

- Provide FAQs about the services.
- Activate NEANIAS usage accounting.
- Activate NEANIAS monitoring.
- Integrate NEANIAS Monitoring with EOSC Availability and Reliability monitoring.
- Integrate NEANIAS usage accounting with EOSC Accounting.
- Define NEANIAS services CRM processes.
- Add support for customised SLAs and OLAs.
- Improve software documentation.
- Extend NEANIAS Helpdesk.

Provisional timeline: Finish by M32.

Cycle 3 activities are in progress for each thematic service independently and follow the maturity of each service.

Additionally, the following table presents up-to-date information on the integration/connection of NEANIAS (core) services with EOSC equivalent/ relevant ones:

EOSC service areas		NEANIAS Service
1. EOSC Portal		NEANIAS catalogue portal
2. Federation services	EOSC AAI Availability and reliability monitoring Usage accounting (compute and storage) Helpdesk (ticketing system)	NEANIAS AAI NEANIAS specific test probes using ARGO service NEANIAS Accounting No interface. NEANIAS will use its own Helpdesk system. Integration to be revisited in the future.
3. Research data management services	Compute, storage, transfer, analysis, PIDs, etc.) Zenodo (research output catalogue + PID)	GARR Cloud Service Catalogue Research Data Repository and Catalogue Data Management based on ARGOS
4. Service Management	EOSC SMS:	NEANIAS SMS defined in D8.2 [29]:

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EOSC service areas		NEANIAS Service
System (SMS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service management processes defined using FitSM Respective implementation tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service management processes and procedures defined using FitSM Implementation tools defined and developed (Section 5.4 and D8.2 [29])

Last but not least, as the NEANIAS services have already achieved a certain level of maturity, their registration on EOSC portal and marketplace is in progress. At the time of writing this document, five (5) thematic services have already been made available on EOSC marketplace, while the majority of the remaining thematic services (as well as some of the core services) are expected to be onboarded to EOSC by the end of 2021, as shown in the following table:

Service name	Lead Provider	Expected EOSC onboarding date
THEMATIC SERVICES		
Underwater services		
U1 - Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data	TELEDYNE	Q4 2021
U2 - Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data	CORONIS	Onboarded ¹¹
U3 - Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data	ATHENA	Onboarded ¹²
Atmosphere services		
A1 – Greenhouse Gases Flux Density Monitoring	ATHENA	Onboarded ¹³
A2 – Monitor atmospheric Perturbations and Components in Active Tectonic Regions		
<i>Atmo-Stress</i>	UNIMIB	Q4 2021
<i>Atmo-Seism</i>	UNIMIB	Q4 2021
A3 – Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting	UBIWHERE	Q4 2021
Space services		
S1 - FAIR Data Management and Visualization for Complex Data and Metadata		
<i>SPACE-VIS ViaLactea Service</i>	INAF	Onboarded ¹⁴
<i>SPACE-VIS ADN Service</i>	ALTEC	Q2 2022
<i>ADAM-SPACE</i>	JACOBS	Q4 2021
S2 - Map making and mosaicing for multidimensional image	MEEO	Q1 2022

¹¹ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/uw-mos/details>
¹² <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/uw-map/details>
¹³ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/atmo-flud/details>
¹⁴ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/space-vis-vialactea-service>

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Service name	Lead Provider	Expected EOSC onboarding date
S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques		
<i>SPACE-ML CAESAR service</i>	INAF	Onboarded ¹⁵
<i>SPACE-ML AstroML service</i>	INAF	Q2 2022
CORE SERVICES		
C3 Artificial Intelligence services		
C3.1 AI Science Gateway: service for development of ML models using Jupyter Hub	SZTAKI	Plan to be defined in Q4 2021
C3.2 Serving trained ML models	ALTEC	Plan to be defined in Q4 2021
C3.3 Distributed Multi-GPU training of large ML models using Horovod	SZTAKI	Plan to be defined in Q4 2021
C3.4 Distributed Machine Learning using SparkML	UNIMIB	Plan to be defined in Q4 2021
C4 Visualisation services		
C4.1 Framework for Visual Discovery (VD)		
<i>VD-VisIVO</i>	INAF	Q4 2021
<i>VD-Splotch</i>	UoP	Q4 2021
<i>VD-Maps</i>	CORONIS	Q4 2021
C4.2 Visualisation Gateway (VG)	INAF	Q4 2021
C4.3 Toolkit for Cross Realities (XR)	ALTEC	N/A
C4.4 Spatial Data Stores (DS)	JACOBS	Plan to be defined in Q4 2021

¹⁵ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/space-ml-caesar-service/details>

7. Conclusions

Since the release of Deliverable D8.1 [28] in July 2020, a lot of developments both at the EOSC level and at NEANIAS services have been realised. At the EOSC level, the developments mainly refer to the governance model and the future development of EOSC. EOSC federated services, targeted for integration by NEANIAS, remain practically unchanged. On the other hand, NEANIAS thematic services have matured over time and new releases have been made available. Additionally, thematic services are being integrating with core ones, which in turn are integrated with EOSC relevant services, where this was considered useful and/or effective.

As derived from the information presented in section 6, the EOSC integration plan of July 2021 is still valid, and the integration of NEANIAS with EOSC is progressing quite smoothly and according to it:

1. Thematic services are in the process of onboarding EOSC, with four (4) of them already available on EOSC marketplace, and the others having planned EOSC onboarding until the end of 2021.
2. NEANIAS core services have already established integration with EOSC relevant ones in the areas of AAI, accounting, monitoring. Moreover, the integration of NEANIAS services with EOSC Research Data Management services is in progress, having already identified the respective requirements, as they are derived from the needs of NEANIAS services.
3. The NEANIAS service management system has been defined and made available to all NEANIAS service providers for application. On top, a helpdesk system has been setup and customised in order to support the execution of the processes and procedures defined by the NEANIAS SMS.

As the EOSC landscape is constantly evolving, NEANIAS will stay open for new integration opportunities offered by EOSC, and reconsider/update its own integration roadmap as needed in the future. D8.4 (due at month 25) will be the next formal checkpoint for assessing the progress of activities towards EOSC integration.

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